

Association between *KRAS* or *PIK3CA* mutations and progesterone resistance on endometriotic epithelial cell line.

Supplementary materials

Table S1. Description of primary antibodies

Antibody	Manufacturer	Clone No.	Dilution	MW (kDa)
Progesterone Receptor A/B Antibody	Cell signaling	3176 (product No.)	1:1000	90 (PR-A) 118 (PR-B)
Progesterone Receptor B	Cell signaling	C1A2	1:1000	118
GAPDH	Wako	5A12	1:1000	37

Table S2. The primers used for real-time qPCR

Gene	Forward primer (5' to 3')	Reverse primer (3' to 5')
<i>COX-2</i>	CGGTGAAACTCTGGCTAGACAG	GCAAACCGTAGATGCTCAGGGA
<i>mPGES-1</i>	GGAACGACATGGAGACCATCTAC	TCCAG GCGACAAAAGGGTTA
<i>IL-6</i>	AGACAGCCACTCACCTCTTCAG	TTCTGCCAGTGCCTCTTTGCTG
<i>MCP-1</i>	AGAATCACCAGCAGCAAGTGTC	TCCTGAACCCACTTCTGCTTGG
<i>VEGF</i>	TGCAGATTATGCGGATCAAACC	TGCATTACATTTGTTGTGCTGTAG
<i>CYP19A1</i>	GACGCAGGATTTCCACAGAAGAG	ATGGTGTCAGGAGCTGCGATCA
<i>GAPDH</i>	TGTTGCCATCAATGACCCCTT	CTCCACGACGTACTIONCAGCG

Figure S1. Presentative fields of migration assay at 200× magnification.

Figure S2. Presentative fields of invasion assay at 200× magnification.